

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGENZI****FIRST NAME: JEAN MONET****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word Office 365 for Mac

7 key concepts:

1. Organizing your ideas and writing the essay (EUCLID 2021, 9-11)
2. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 13-14)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-40)
5. Style guide and its importance (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)5/24/25 6:32:00 PM

BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I had a great experience reading through the ACA-401D Period 1's materials, namely the ACA-401 Coursepack, Basic ACA-401 Tutorial video, and Instructor's Sample Review Video. I consider the ACA-401 Coursepack for Period 1 as a handbook full of great principles and guidelines that will help me accomplish my writing assignments throughout my learning journey. This essay will discuss the five main takeaways from Period 1's Coursepack. I will highlight my understanding of each takeaway and reflect on how it is essential in my studies at EUCLID. The five takeaways to discuss are: writing the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-11), some rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 13-14), punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23), plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39), and the style guide and its importance (EUCLID 2021, 40-42).

2) ORGANIZING YOUR IDEAS AND WRITING THE ESSAY

Writing an essay is a step-by-step process that consists of creating an essay plan and using it to organize your ideas (EUCLID 2021, 9). The essay plan serves as a guide to draft the essay. Organizing ideas when writing an essay is a crucial step. I consider this step as creating a survey plan of your house before starting the actual construction work. Without a clear survey plan or scheme of a house, there is no direction or guide to follow to build a house. Comparatively, organizing ideas and outlining the main elements to discuss in the essay play a significant role in the design of the essay plan or structure. The essay plan, being a tool, helps to reflect on and identify the answer/s that will be given to essay question/s, choose the suitable topics or ideas to discuss in my answer/s, put together details and examples to support my ideas, and determine how I will organize my ideas in the essay (EUCLID 2021, 9–10). This is an excellent step in essay writing as it makes it easy for the author to start their essay with an end in mind. I like this method, and it will always be helpful for me to write my essay draft by following the plan.

Typically, an essay should have an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). Each component of the essay must follow a clear structure. An introduction needs to present what the essay is about (main ideas), provide a response to the question given (thesis statement), and give a summary of the whole essay (summary) (EUCLID 2021, 10). The essay's body is where the main ideas are elaborated with supporting details, evidence, and examples (EUCLID 2021, 10). For instance, in the open response paper, I will describe my reaction and understanding of each thing (idea) out of my chosen 5 – 7 things I learned from the study materials. Lastly, the conclusion comes later in the essay. In conclusion, the answer to the question must be highlighted along with a summary of the whole essay by focusing on the main ideas discussed in the body (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Moreover, it is important to organize the paragraphs well in the essay. Each paragraph needs to have a topic sentence presenting the main idea, along with sentences explaining the main idea in more detail. These sentences should present evidence or examples supporting the main idea presented in the topic sentence. Following the evidence, the author must add his analysis and reaction and close the paragraph by summarizing the main idea, evidence, and reaction (EUCLID 2021, 11). For now, I will be able to use the essay plan to draft my essay and make sure my paragraphs have all the critical sentences. These include a topic sentence with the main idea, an explanation of the main idea along with evidence and examples, my analysis and reaction to the main idea and its evidence, and a sentence concluding the paragraph.

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

There are three Do's and Don'ts or rules of thumb that stood out most for me when reding the coursepark. Firstly, when writing a paper, the thesis needs to be stated in the introduction of the paper (EUCLID 2021, 13). This is crucial as it guides readers to know

what the paper is about and the author's position. The thesis also helps the writer to stay focused and follow the proper writing structure.

Secondly, the author should write clearly. This is done by using short sentences (not more than five lines), short paragraphs (not more than 20 lines), and simple words to help readers understand presented ideas (EUCLID 2021, 13). This is a great rule to apply in writing. I already started to benefit from the Grammarly premium application provided by EUCLID. Hence, I will strive to present my ideas concisely and precisely. I often struggle with writing short paragraphs, but I will do my best to reduce the number of lines in my paragraph by sticking to the structure of the essay and paragraph described above under point 2).

Thirdly, the author should always avoid plagiarism. This may happen when one uses information from another paper or article as they are and does not use quotation marks or when they draw ideas from another essay or article and use them without citing by using footnotes (EUCLID 2021, 13). This rule is essential in writing, given that plagiarism brings academic penalties. I take this rule seriously and plan to implement it by always acknowledging used sources in my essays/papers through in-text and reference citations. I appreciate the resources provided already by EUCLID on how to cite using Zotero. I benefit from this resource to cite appropriately and avoid plagiarism.

4) PUNCTUATIONS

Punctuations are significant in writing and presenting ideas clearly in papers or essays. There are many punctuations, but I will discuss three types that stood out to me when reading the study material and reflect on how I plan to use them in my writing. Those are apostrophes to show possession and contraction; bullet points to list items, full stops, exclamation marks, and question marks to indicate the end of a sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16).

The general rule for using punctuation is to use a small number of punctuations in a sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16). I agree with this rule because the more punctuation the author uses in their sentence, the more the sentence changes from simple to more complex or compound. Apostrophes indicate the possession of something or an action by a specific subject. In this case, the format changes based on whether the subject ends by s or z. For instance, I may say, 'Monet's computer is overheated due to overusing it.' I may also say, 'Many cows' horns in Africa tend to be very long.' Possessive pronouns (its) and some place names with St or Saint can create confusion (EUCLID 2021, 16). For instance, 'I drive a Toyota car, but its engine is a Honda.' This 'its' should remain as it is because it denotes that the engine belongs to the car. Apostrophes are also used to show contractions. For instance, I may say, 'My child doesn't like ice cream.' Doesn't is a contraction form of 'does not.' I will apply these rules and use apostrophes appropriately to avoid confusion and mechanical errors.

Bullet points are another type of punctuation that is used to list items. The bullet points should not have a full stop at the end of each item. However, if the list and its

introductory phrase make a complete sentence, a full stop is added at the end of the list (the last item). Furthermore, a semi-colon at the of each item of the list when one item is a complete sentence (EUCLID 2021, 18). It is interesting how one sentence in the list changes the punctuation format of all the bullet points. These rules are crucial in writing, and I admit that I did not know them, yet I like to use bullet points in my papers. From now on, I will create bullet points with appropriate punctuation.

Lastly, using full stops, exclamation marks, and question marks to end a sentence is essential in writing. I found that using an exclamation mark for imperative form is very interesting. Imperative sentences sound like a declaration, and I thought a full stop was the appropriate punctuation to use on them. I know these are commands more than declarations, but I still find this an interesting rule. Moreover, not using a full stop before or after ellipsis is another interesting rule (EUCLID 2021, 18). I realized that I made mistakes in the past around these three punctuations, but from now on, I will correct my mistakes.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is a critical academic violation in writing. It is about not acknowledging authors or sources that one uses their works (words, ideas, images, etc.) to write his/hers. (EUCLID 2021, 34). For instance, if I use content from another source in my paper either by copying or paraphrasing and do not acknowledge the authors of sources where I get the content from, that is plagiarism. Although plagiarism is considered a big academic violation, when one cites appropriately their work, there is no way to fall into the violation. Acknowledging other authors and sources in our works is not only academically required but also ethically correct. Being academically honest and attributing credits to other authors is a good trait we should all aim to have and maintain.

Citing properly, both in-text and in reference or works cited lists, protects people from plagiarism in their work (EUCLID 2021, 34–35). In-text citation is done to cite quotations or paraphrases used in the work from another source or author. This is done in different ways and formats based on the rule of citation style chosen. However, the common elements of the in-text citation generally remain the same. These are the author or source name, year of publication, and page number in parentheses added next to the paraphrase and quoted text or paragraph. If the quote is longer than four lines, it is treated as a paragraph and formatted by RP Quote style (EUCLID 2021, 35). The citation style rule dictates the format and elements for works cited or reference lists. Based on the cited source's nature, the citation's format and components change accordingly. For example, a citation format for a book differs from a video or an online article's (EUCLID 2021, 38). Lastly, citation in references can also be done using footnotes. At EUCLID, this is done, most especially in major papers.

In my past academic journeys, I wrote short and long papers. I was citing by using the APA citation style rule. I neither used Zotero nor Chicago style (Turabian), only APA format and citation style, MS Word citation machine, and online citation generator tools. In my journey at EUCLID, having Zotero, materials with guidance on academic writing

and citation, such as the coursepack of ACA-401D Period 1, and other orientation materials with instructions and expectations to meet, is beneficial. Hence, I am committed to paraphrasing, quoting other sources or authors, and citing them properly to avoid plagiarism.

6)STYLE GUIDE AND ITS IMPORTANCE

A style guide in writing is an excellent tool consisting of rules and principles to follow when writing and formatting publications or papers. An author or authors from a publishing house or company follow the guide for consistency purposes (EUCLID 2021, 41). For instance, all papers must follow Chicago rules and use American English at EUCLID. This is important to EUCLID in different ways, and I will describe them below.

Having one style guide helps the writer's and the university's papers and publications be written and formatted similarly (consistency). Moreover, having a unique style guide helps writers follow a similar structure when writing, making it easy to format all papers uniformly. I believe this even increases the brand awareness of the organization's work through its publications. On the other hand, this may limit people's creativity and innovation in their writing (EUCLID 2021, 41). For instance, following a similar style guide feels like filling content into a ready and formatted template. One can argue that this can limit how they express their thoughts and ideas due to being limited to a single writing style. However, I believe that the focus of writing should be the content and ideas being expressed, not necessarily how the paper is formatted. Thus, I strongly support using one style guide as an author or an organization for consistency. Lastly, on the side of EUCLID as an academic institution, having one style guide eases planning and preparing course materials, providing feedback on students' works, and providing support. For instance, if there were no writing guidelines or templates to use when writing papers, each student would come up with their paper format, citation rule, and writing principles. I can imagine how difficult it would be for the institution and teachers to prepare students similarly and assess their written work.

7)CONCLUSION

To sum up, academic essay and paper writing require numerous principles and rules, from organizing ideas, creating an essay plan, and using it to draft your essay, using punctuation properly, citing paraphrases and quotes appropriately to avoid plagiarism, following a provided style guide, and many others. Each rule or principle plays a big role in writing a good essay and is considered under the basics of essay or paper writing. The rules mentioned above are part of the style guide, which should be respected in writing to keep consistency in all the works. I found these basics of writing as beneficial tools to guide me when writing my short and long papers at EUCLID. Reflecting on the 5 things I chose to focus on in this paper, I realized that I need to exercise each in my writing and master it so that my papers will always be academically well-written and readable to my audience.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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